

MODE I FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP LAMINATE TOUGHENED WITH CNF INTERLAYER

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers have received a great deal of attention in the aeronautical, biological, electrical and mechanical sciences, and engineering fields. They are suitable for this application as they also have excellent mechanical properties such as elastic moduli, strength, fracture toughness, and flexibility compared with the traditional carbon fiber which are based on polyacrylonitrile (PAN). In the present study, we implemented an alternative way to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue property of CFRP laminates by inserting carbon nanofiber interlayer in the unidirectional CFRP laminates. Carbon nanofiber was employed as reinforcement for the interlayers for mode I fracture toughness tests. Carbon nanofiber, MWNT-7 (Hodogaya Chemical Co., LTD.), were used for the reinforcement of the CFRP laminate. Base material of unidirectional carbon fiber was used as main composition materials in the present study. The static and fatigue properties of mode I crack was investigated by double cantilever beam (DCB) tests. The experimental results showed that the interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue crack growth resistance can be improved by inserting the CNF interlayer on the Unidirectional CFRP laminates fabricated by VaRTM process and the results were compared with base laminate (No CNF interlayer) and those obtained by woven fabric.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have been developed as the foremost material for products in fields such as mechanical, electrical, architectural, and structural engineering. Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has especially attained a prominent position in use as structural materials for aeronautical and space engineering. Application in this industry requires further reduction in weight to satisfy the demand for higher fuel efficiency.

Recently, a number of experimental and analytical techniques have been proposed to evaluate the fracture toughness for mode I[1], mode II[2], mixed mode[3] with several combinations of carbon fiber and matrix resin. Previous attempts to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates has shown various useful results. Namely, a certain level of toughening technique has already been achieved by inserting an interleaf (interlayer) between the CFRP Prepregs[4]. T800H/3900-2, with a heterogeneous interlayer consisting of fine thermo plastic particles, has shown high compressive strength after impact (CAI). Ionomer interleaved CFRP laminates have shown higher toughness under mode I[5] and II deformations[6].

In recent years, carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers have received a great deal of attention in the aeronautical, biological, electrical and mechanical sciences, and engineering fields. Since discovery of the carbon nanotube in the 1970s[7,8] and the publication in Nature[9] clarifying the structure of the carbon nanofibers, carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers have received a great deal of attention in the aeronautical, biological, electrical and mechanical sciences, and engineering fields.

Due to CNF's superiority in electrical conductivity, MWCNT or vapor grown carbon fiber 'VGCF' has established a strong presence in the storage battery field as the conductive filler. Carbon nanotubes and nanofibers have been applied as the toughening filler of the structural material for resin or metal based composites[10,11]. They are suitable for this application as they also have excellent mechanical properties such as elastic moduli, strength, fracture toughness, and flexibility compared with the traditional carbon fiber which are based on polyacrylonitrile (PAN).

In the present study, we implemented an alternative way to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue property of CFRP laminates by inserting carbon nanofibers between the unidirectional CFRP laminates[12,13]. Carbon nanofiber was employed as reinforcement for the interlayers for mode I fracture toughness tests. MWNT-7(Hodogaya Chemical Co.,LTD.) was used for the reinforcement of the CFRP laminate. The carbon fiber of unidirectional fabric was used as main composition materials in the present study.

The static and fatigue property of mode I crack was investigated by double cantilever beam (DCB) tests. The experimental results showed that the interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue crack growth resistance can be improved by inserting the CNF interlayer on the unidirectional CFRP laminates

2 CFRP SPECIMENS

Unidirectional fabric of carbon fiber MRK-M2-40 (Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.) has been used for the base material of CFRP. Epoxy resin "DENATOOL" (Nagase Chemtex Corp.) has been used for the matrix, where XNR6809 is base resin and XNH6809 is curing agent. In order to reinforce between the woven fabric layer by making nanofiber/resin interlayer, MWNT-7 (Hodogaya Chemical Co., LTD.) have been introduced. In the CFRP specimens, carbon nanofiber interlayer was inserted between 10th and 11th woven fabric in the vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process .

At first, CNF and epoxy resin were mixed in a planetary centrifugal mixer (SR500, THINKY USA Inc.). The quantity of the CNF was controlled by area density of CNF [g/m^2]. When the area density of CNF is X [g/m^2], the weight fraction of the CNF should be controlled to wt[%] in the mixed epoxy/CNF. After making a pair of the preform composed of 10 layer woven fabric, the mixed epoxy/CNF was applied on the preform and the preforms were stacked inserting polyimide film (Thickness $30\mu\text{m}$) to make an artificial crack in the CFRP laminate as shown in Fig.1.

Wrapping up the preform by sealant tape and bagging film, then epoxy resin is put in the preform with vacuum assist. After filling up with resin in the woven fabric preform, resin was cured by heating in an electric furnace. Primary curing is 2 hours by 80°C in 4 hours, and it carried out secondary curing is 2 hours by 120°C .

From the CFRP laminate obtained by VaRTM process, a CFRP laminated beams (20mm width, 150mm length) were cut out for the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens for the fracture toughness tests and fatigue crack propagation tests. DCB specimens in the present study are shown in the Table 1.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In the present study, fracture toughness tests for crack opening mode (Mode I) have been carried out (Fig.2). For static mode I test, a universal material testing machine AGS-J-5kN, SHIMADZU Co. was used. The aluminum tabs were attached to the opening end of a DCB specimen, and the mode I tests were carried out by giving compulsive displacement to the DCB specimen through a pair of hinge, where the cross head rate was specified to 0.5mm/min. On the other hand, an electric fatigue testing machine Electro Pulse E3000, Instron Co. was used for the fatigue crack propagation tests of mode I. The fatigue tests were carried out with load control of the frequency 5Hz where the maximum and minimum loads were specified to 42N and 8.4N (load ratio = 0.2),

Figure 1: A picture and schematic of VaRTM

Table 1: CFRP Specimens for DCB tests

Specimen	CNF Type	Amount of CNF [g/m ²]	Thickness [mm]
Base Laminate	-	-	3.76
MWNT7-10	MWNT-7	10	3.99
MWNT7-20	MWNT-7	20	3.96
MWNT7-30	MWNT-7	30	4.11

respectively. The fracture toughness of the DCB testing were evaluated by modified compliance calibration method[14,15]. The side section of the specimen was ground by the Emery paper and it was painted white to observe the crack extension. Observing the crack front by the digital camera (SONY α 700 with close-up lens), the crack length was measured continuously in the DCB tests.

4 STATIC MODE I TESTS

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were carried out using INSTRON ElectroPulse E3000. From the relation applied load and COD (crack opening displacement), we have the relation between fracture toughness and crack growth Δa as shown in Fig.3

Figure 2: Mode I static DCB tests.

Figure 3: Relation between fracture toughness G_{Ic} and crack growth Δa .

In the Fig. 3 the fracture toughness G_{Ic} was estimated by modified compliance calibration method. The fracture toughness of CFRP/MWNT-7 laminates increase 60-70% of base CFRP laminate in the initial stage of crack propagation.

As the cracks extend, the difference G_{Ic} (Interlayer) and G_{Ic} (Base laminate) became small. G_{Ic} (Interlayer) and G_{Ic} (Base laminate) becomes 1.2 – 1.3 in the region of the steady state of crack propagation (Δa :50–70mm). We can see that, the area density of CNF 10g/m² and 20g/m² give relatively high fracture toughness as shown in Fig.3.

5 MODE I FATIGUE TESTSS

Mode I fatigue crack growth tests were carried out for CFRP laminate toughened with MWNT-7 interlayer. Figures 4 and 5 show the relation between the extension of the crack length Δa and cycles for the mode I crack fatigue tests. The number of cycles which results in final unstable fracture increased sharply using MWNT-7 interlayer.

Figure 4: Relation between the crack growth Δa and cycles for the mode I crack fatigue tests (results of N=4 for each specimens).

Figure 5: Relation between the crack growth Δa and cycles for the mode I crack fatigue tests (summary of typical results).

Figure 6: Relation between the crack propagation rate $\Delta a/\Delta N$ and energy release rate range ΔG_I (results of N=4 for each specimens).

Figure 7 Relation between the crack propagation rate $\Delta a/\Delta N$ and energy release rate range ΔG_I (summary of typical results).

In the base CFRP laminate, brittle fracture occurred in the experimental final stage. By about 7×10^5 cycles, the base laminate was broken completely. On the other hand, in MWNT-7/CFRP, the brittle fracture was controlled by means of inserting the CNF interlayer and relatively slow crack propagation was observed until the crack reach 80 mm in length.

Relationship between crack propagation rate da/dN and the energy release rate range ΔG_I is shown in Figs.6 and 7. Here, da/dN for all MWNT laminates for the initial region with a small energy release rate $100 < \Delta G_I < 300$ [J/m^2] and that for the latter region with a large energy release rate $300 < \Delta G_I < 1000$ [J/m^2] are considered, respectively.

In the initial region ($100 < \Delta G_I < 300$ [J/m^2]), the crack propagation rate of MWNT-7/CFRP decreased as compared with the case of base laminate. Although there is large scatter in these data, the crack propagation rate of MWNT-7/CFRP is about 1/10 of the base laminate case. On the other hand, in the latter region $300 < \Delta G_I < 1000$ [J/m^2], the crack propagation rate of MWNT-7/CFRP is relatively low as compared with the base laminate case. However, the great difference cannot be admitted in the crack propagation tendencies. The so great difference can't admit to be shown in a chart between MWNT-7/CFRP and Base laminate for the inclination in the relation between the crack development rate and the destruction toughness value. The so great difference cannot be confirmed between MWNT-7/CFRP and base laminate for the gradient of the relation between crack propagation rate $\log(da/dN)$ and energy release rate range ΔG_I .

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, mode I fracture toughness and mode I fatigue crack property of unidirectional CFRP laminate toughened with carbon nanofiber interlayer (MWNT-7) have been investigated. The static mode I fracture toughness of CNF/CFRP laminates increased 60-70% of that in the base laminates at the initial stage of the crack propagation in the MWNT-7 case. In the domain in which the crack fully progressed, the fracture toughness increased 20-30% of that in the base laminate.

For the mode I fatigue crack tests, the number of cycles which a final fracture produces increased to 3 -5 times compared with the case of base laminate by using CNF interlayer. The fracture toughness (upper limit of the energy release rate range $\Delta G_{I_{max}}$) in fatigue crack extension amounts to 1000 [J/m^2] in the MWNT-7/CFRP and base laminate. In the initial region ($100 < \Delta G_I < 300$ [J/m^2]), the crack propagation rate of MWNT-7/CFRP decreased to half of the case of base laminate. In the latter region ($300 < \Delta G_I < 1000$ [J/m^2]), although crack propagation rate of the MWNT-7/CFRP seems to be slightly low compared with base laminate, the great difference cannot be admitted in the crack propagation tendencies.

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